

Dedication of a Professional Educative Personnel in Applying the Independent Curriculum

Hamzah^{1*}, Nur'aini²

Sekolah Tinggi Agama Islam Ibnu Sina Batam

Corresponding Author: Hamzah drhamzah@uis.ac.id

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ABSTRACT

Implementation of the Independent Curriculum will not work properly without teachers who have adequate capacity to implement the curriculum. Therefore, this research was conducted to identify and analyze the factors that influence teacher capacity building in implementing the Independent Curriculum. With the idea of the independent learning program by the Minister of Education and Culture Nadiem Anwar Makarim as a form of improving the quality of education in Indonesia, teachers must be able to carry out their duties with full responsibility in carrying out their duties, so that educational goals can run well according to what is aspired to. . To make this happen, teachers must have working professionals from: 1) designing and implementing an independent curriculum, 2) driving teachers and 3) overcoming obstacles to implementing an independent curriculum.

INTRODUCTION

The presence of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Nadiem Makarim sparked an idea for a change in curriculum, namely the independent learning curriculum. The independent learning curriculum is one of the curriculum concepts that demands independence for students. Independence in the sense that each learner is given the freedom to access knowledge obtained from formal and non-formal education. In this curriculum, it does not limit the concept of learning that takes place at school or outside of school and also requires the creativity of teachers and students. (Ansari et al., 2022).

The presence of this independent learning curriculum also aims to answer the challenges of education in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 where in its realization it must support skills in critical thinking and problem solving, creative and innovative, as well as being skilled in communicating and collaborating for students. (Ansari et al., 2022).

Independent learning requires teachers, students, and parents to build a happy atmosphere in their environment. Merdeka Learning returns educational literacy to its core as a strategic momentum to realize the goals of National Education. (Desrianti & Nelisma, 2022). However, the implementation of the Independent Curriculum will not work properly without teachers who have adequate capacity to implement the curriculum. Therefore, this research was conducted to identify and analyze the factors that influence teacher capacity building in implementing the Independent Curriculum. (Suryaningrum, 2023). It is important to have professional educators to answer the challenges of education in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 in the independent curriculum. So the research question is how dedicated are the teaching staff in applying the independent curriculum professionally.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Dedication

Dedication in English, dedicate means to offer. In the Big Indonesian Dictionary it is explained that "Dedication is devotion that is sacrificing energy, thought, and time for success with noble goals" (Depdiknas, 2007).

This dedication can also mean dedication to carry out noble ideals and requires a firm belief. "Dedication is the contribution of ideas and energy given by employees sincerely to the company. The higher the employee's dedication to the company, the higher the employee's loyalty" (Wilianto, 2019).H1: Hypothesis one and so on here

Educative Power

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Independent Curriculum

Curriculum is a set of plans and arrangements regarding objectives, content, and learning materials as well as materials used as guidelines for organizing learning activities to achieve certain educational goals. (Bafadhhol, 2017). Merdeka Curriculum is a diverse learning intracurricular curriculum in which content will be optimized to provide sufficient time for students to investigate concepts and build competencies. In order for learning to be tailored to the needs and interests of students, teachers can choose from a variety of teaching tools. (Desrianti & Nelisma, 2022).

METHODOLOGY

This study uses a literature review approach with qualitative methods. Literature review research is research that processes and collects research materials in the form of library data that can be obtained from books or journals. This research was conducted to examine theories related to independent learning as an effort to improve the quality of learning in schools/madrasas. The data was obtained from various sources, including books, theses, dissertations, scientific papers and other sources. Thus, all sources of data and information can be utilized optimally in developing ideas that are relevant to research. (Rahmasyah, 2021).

RESEARCH RESULT

Eductive Energy Dedication to Independent Learning

A. Learning Design

In the independent learning program the teacher must have free and independent thinking in designing existing learning according to the needs of students. Teachers have independence in choosing elements of the curriculum to be developed in the learning process according to the needs of students. The freedom that the teacher has in choosing the elements in the curriculum must be able to create learning that challenges students to have critical thinking in solving various existing problems, be able to foster creative creativity and have good character in establishing communication and collaboration with other people. (Desrianti & Nelisma, 2022).

In an effort to create independent learning for students, of course the teacher must be able to use his creative power in designing learning using various existing learning methods and media. The learning process will be interesting and fun if the teacher is able to design learning creatively. Teachers can choose suitable methods by using learning media to help students understand and understand the material being taught. With a variety of learning methods and the use of appropriate learning media will create learning that is not monotonous. Thus, the goals and policies of the government regarding independent learning will be achieved properly. (Desrianti & Nelisma, 2022).

B. Implementation of Learning

Teacher commitment is a teacher's emotional attachment to the school where he works so that he is willing to survive, identify himself and be involved in achieving school goals (Hidayat, 2017b). There are several types of commitment related to teachers, namely: professional commitment, commitment to students and commitment to society. The form of teacher commitment consists of: personal goal, namely the teacher has a commitment to be the best, capacity belief, namely believing in one's own abilities, context belief, namely the teacher's ability to utilize learning resources effectively and efficiently, and emotional arousal process, namely the ability to be ready to carry out tasks under any circumstances. (Sari, 2019).

Teacher commitment is also related to organizational commitment. Organizational commitment is the emotional attachment of employees to identify and be involved in the organization. Stoch et al. states that organizational commitment is an ongoing process in which employees express concern for the success of the organization in which they work. (Sari, 2019).

Based on the study of the concepts and theories above, it can be concluded that the teacher's commitment is the expression and efforts of the teacher in a continuous time in advancing students and the school with indicators: (1) Maintaining parents' trust in the school; (2) Monitor the development and progress of students; (3) Trying to attend school; (4) Trying to be present on time; (5) Feeling proud of the school; (6) Maintaining a good name through attitude and behavior; (7) Helping school academic progress; (8) Maintaining a conducive climate in schools; (9) Committed to being a good teacher; (10) Provide useful subject matter for students; (11) Treat students as unique and valuable; (12) Trying to become a professional teacher. (Sari, 2019).

C. Dedication of Educative Personnel as a Mobilizing Teacher

So to realize this independent learning program, the government created a program called the driving teacher, namely to move teachers to carry out their duties as teachers in independent learning learning. With the development of educational policies, of course teachers must be able to adapt to the policies that apply, especially in curriculum changes. Although in its application, it is certain that it will have some problems because the Free Learning Curriculum is still relatively new and not all schools at the elementary school level apply this Free Learning Curriculum. In the Free Learning Curriculum, learning is determined by the teacher so that teachers must get out of their comfort zone or change the paradigm from traditional learning to more creative learning because the ultimate goal of learning activities is to shape the character of students according to the Pancasila Student Profile. (Zulaiha et al., 1925).

D. Obstacles to the Dedication of Educative Personnel to the Independent Curriculum

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers, several obstacles were found in implementing the independent curriculum including:

- 1) Lack of Government Dissemination of Independent Curriculum to

Schools. The government did hold webinars and training on the independent curriculum, but the webinar and training only explained the importance of the concept of independent learning in the independent curriculum, even though what schools and teachers need is how to apply point to point in the learning process. And if the teacher asks what he doesn't understand to a webinar or training resource person, the answers from the resource person are not satisfactory to answer the teacher's anxiety, so the teachers don't really understand the application of the learning process to the independent curriculum concept.

- 2) Lack of Teacher Preparation to Switch to the Independent Curriculum. Teachers realize that they have insufficient experience in using learning tools in the teaching and learning process, experience should be a form of preparation to increase the professionalism of a teacher in obtaining new experiences in order to update his competence and professional skills (Ihsan, 2022: 37). Many schools have just implemented the revised 2013 curriculum so they have to go back to mastering a different curriculum. If in the 2013 curriculum there are targeted competencies contained in KI, KD which must be achieved annually, in the independent curriculum the intended competencies are contained in learning outcomes arranged per phase.
- 3) Learning Resources Are Only Limited in Package Books. Because the independent curriculum has not yet become the national curriculum, the books purchased by schools are also incomplete because this curriculum is still experimental and still receiving feedback from schools that use it so that at any time the textbooks can change both the content and edition so that schools take the initiative not to buy textbooks first. curriculum merdeka with complete editions and also in the nearest bookstore there are no such books. Apart from that the teacher is also still confused about using what learning media is appropriate for teaching students, even so the teacher also always tries to facilitate learning with media and teaching materials that are interesting in learning.(Wantiana, 2023).

DISCUSSION

The concept of the independent learning policy is that teachers as educators are able to create a comfortable learning atmosphere and are able to arouse enthusiasm for learning so that students do not feel burdened by the material presented by the teacher. (Yusuf & Arfiansyah, 2021) In the Free Learning Curriculum, a teacher is required to be creative and innovative in designing learning. In creating independent learning for students, a teacher must be able to use his creativity in designing learning using various existing learning methods and media. The learning process will be interesting and fun if a teacher is able to design learning creatively and innovatively. Teachers can choose learning methods that are suitable for students and use learning media

so that students will more easily understand and understand the material being taught.(Zulaiha et al., 1925).

With the development of educational policies, of course teachers must be able to adapt to the policies that apply, especially in curriculum changes. Although in its application, it is certain that it will have some problems because the Free Learning Curriculum is still relatively new and not all schools at the elementary school level apply this Free Learning Curriculum.(Zulaiha et al., 1925).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The teacher is one of the most important components in the teaching and learning process, which plays a role in the effort to form superior and intelligent human resources intellectually and spiritually according to the mandate of the independent curriculum and the profile of independent students. With the idea of the independent learning program by the Minister of Education and Culture Nadiem Anwar Makarim as a form of improving the quality of education in Indonesia, teachers must be able to carry out their duties with full responsibility in carrying out their duties, so that educational goals can run well according to what is aspired to. . To make this happen, teachers must have working professionals from: 1) designing and implementing an independent curriculum, 2) driving teachers and 3) overcoming obstacles to implementing an independent curriculum.

In order to welcome the independent learning curriculum program, teachers must have at least four competencies, all of which have their respective functions and roles. Without competence, a teacher is like a captain in the middle of the ocean without sufficient expertise, while in front of him high waves are ready to roll over the ship.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

This research is based on a literature review based on field studies conducted by a number of researchers, each research result is of course based on different conclusions, but common threads can be drawn regarding the problems and ideals of implementing an independent curriculum. There should be further research on the different realities and problems in the implementation of the independent curriculum at different levels and regional demographics.

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